

DISCOVER YOUR GUINNESS STORY: REPURPOSING A DIGITAL PRESERVATION SYSTEM INTO A HISTORICAL DATABASE

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Abstract - The Guinness Archive embarked on a project in 2024 to create a public facing, user-friendly historical database consisting of 250,000 digitised images and 1.6 million individual metadata records.

The project encompassed partnerships with Ancestry, Preservica and web agencies to deliver an intuitive search powered by Preservica's digital repository software and accessible free of charge via the Guinness Storehouse website.

The paper explores the technical steps involved, challenges and opportunities, lessons learned and outcomes. It is an exploration of utilizing digital repository software to serve additional business needs within a digital preservation environment.

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Conference Topics - Tūhono - Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Guinness Archive (the Archive) collects, preserves and shares the history of Guinness from 1759 to the present day. Our extensive collections encompass 7,000 linear metres of company records, which include ledgers, maps, plans, photographs, advertisements, personnel files, and artefacts. As the only corporate archive in Ireland open to the public, we are committed to making these collections accessible as they reflect not just the history of Guinness but also that of Dublin and the wider island of Ireland.

The Archive has been collecting digital records dating back to its formation in 2000. The multimedia collections encompass digitised material, audiovisual material, born-digital records, web archives, 3D models and more - amounting to over 64TB at our most recent collection survey. The Archive submitted a successful business case for a digital preservation system and onboarded Preservica in 2022. We are currently in the process of ingesting digital collections from SharePoint, Microsoft Azure storage and external hard drives for long-term preservation. Ingest work is ongoing and we continue to actively add collections to our public-facing portal [1].

II. ANCESTRY COLLABORATION

The Archive is home to a substantial collection of Guinness Company ledgers. Two series of these ledgers, relating to personnel and customers, were identified as rich resources of historical information that had not been used to their full potential. The ledgers were relatively inaccessible owing to the significant number of volumes and their large physical size.

The Employee Ledgers (1886–1957) digitised as part of the project span a range of functions including attendance logs, labourer's wages, sick leave ledgers, widows and orphans, female employees, and others. The Trade Ledgers (1850–

1968) contain meticulous records of the distribution and sale of Guinness to individual publicans and wholesalers across the islands of Ireland and Great Britain. They include sales further overseas on a smaller scale, including mainland Europe, the United States and more. They essentially act as a census of publicans across the British Isles.

In 2023, we partnered with Ancestry to digitise and index the ledgers collections. The project resulted in 250,000 digital images, amounting to 7TB, and over 1.6 million individual data entries. The record set went live on Ancestry.com in March 2024 to significant international attention, particularly in the United States [2]. The launch made 2.2 billion impressions across 125 online and social stories.

A key stipulation of the partnership was that the Guinness Archive would receive a full set of the digitised images and raw data, with the intention of making them accessible to the public on Guinness-owned channels without a paywall.

III. THE CHALLENGE

The Archive was presented with a challenge to replicate a user-friendly searching experience without having access to Ancestry's resources or infrastructure. The only system that at the Archive's disposal that could comfortably store, manage and interrogate 7TB of data was Preservica. A major stumbling block was that Preservica is designed to function as a digital preservation system and not a historical database. Digital preservation systems are not immediately intuitive for users who are not digital preservation professionals, and a more accessible solution was required.

Internal stakeholders requested that any search interface be hosted on the Guinness Storehouse (GSH) website to keep traffic on internal channels, rather than rerouting users to a third-party site (i.e. Preservica). This meant that any solution with Preservica needed to integrate seamlessly with the website for public access. Faced with a single pathway forward, we set about wrangling a digital preservation system into functioning as a historical database with the Preservica UX team and the web development agency responsible for the design and maintenance of the Guinness Storehouse website.

IV. THE API

Any API calls needed to retrieve not only the relevant search results but return the ledger image without taking the user out of the GSH funnel. Asset retrieval presented another challenge as digital preservation systems are generally designed to prevent the hosting of material on external platforms.

A secondary consideration was that the images themselves are hi-res and quite large digital objects. Our internal web team have a maximum load time for the GSH website and the database search could not impact these return times. The GSH website would not be capable of pulling images through for download without impacting the run time of the site, even if the functionality were technically feasible.

V. INGEST

Ancestry delivered the scanned images and datasets to the Archive via external hard drives in January 2024. The first step was to ingest the digital surrogates into Preservica for digital preservation. The images were packaged using Preservica's Open Preservation Exchange (OPEX) format and Preservation Asset eXchange (PAX) protocol [3]. This prepared the assets for linking with Axiell Collections, the Archive's catalogue and collection management system.⁴ Collections is linked with our instance of Preservica via API. Preservica pulls descriptive metadata through from Collections and the latter functions as the metadata master copy, ensuring that any edits only need to take place once.

The data transfer from external hard drive to computer for packaging, upload to Microsoft Azure and finally ingest into Preservica was extensive. It took a dedicated staff member roughly a month of consistent packaging and running ingest workflows to get the entire 7TB into our preservation environment within Preservica.

VI. METADATA MAPPING

Our initial approach to metadata mapping was to attach each individual entry of metadata directly to its associated digital object (or ledger image) as a fragment. The nature of the ledgers as day-to-day records meant that a single image could be associated with tens of individual metadata

fragments. This made the images searchable within Preservica using the personal names, addresses and dates contained within the fragments.

An API was developed using Preservica's developer tools to run searches entered by the user and call this metadata through the search engine. The web team created a search portal on the Guinness Storehouse test site [4]. Initial results from this approach were mixed. The API was successful in being able to retrieve metadata fragments but, in cases where a field may be empty, data would be 'bumped up' from the next data entry, creating mismatches.

VII. AN ALTERNATIVE APPROACH

A new approach was needed to ensure accuracy of results. We pivoted to re-ingest the Excel dataset with each line of data becoming an individual 'record' within Preservica. The 'Records Database' became its own collection within the repository. Each of the 1.6 million records were then linked to their associated image via their UUID. We mapped the API search to the fields we wanted to be publicly searchable, and testing proved that this solution had been more successful. Searching by surname, date or geographical location returned the results we were expecting.

Image retrieval using the API was tricky and initial attempts using third-party image viewers were unsuccessful. The web tech team were eventually able to use the API to generate a thumbnail representation of the image hosted in Preservica. It is at this later stage in the search where there is a direct link through to Preservica Universal Access should a user want to conduct further research or browse the collections. The search went live in March 2025 following several rounds of internal testing.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Overall, the project has been a significant success in terms of harnessing our available resources to create a user-friendly historical database for our users. The function has not been fully publicized by the Archive but, so far, the functionality has been used by our users to locate relatives, to trace the history of prominent Irish pubs and as the basis of

research into Irish women running pubs across the island of Ireland in the 19th and 20th centuries.

The current API set up is flexible in allowing us to add to this dataset as new collections are keyed or imaged. We have been able to add data produced outside the scope of the Ancestry project to the Records Database and are looking to index future *Transkribus* outputs to fit within the existing metadata field structure.

There were several valuable lessons learned that we will take forward into any future projects. We would bake delivery method of digital files into any future collaborative project from the outset. The additional step in transferring data from external hard drives significantly impacted overall ingest timelines. There was an overall underestimation in the Archive on how long it would take to ingest the digitised ledgers, not only due to their size but also due to the sheer volume of images that needed to be packaged and ingested.

It is essential to ensure that any developers remain in constant communication with the vendor. Digital preservation software is bespoke and specific functionalities or quirks may not be immediately apparent to those not in the industry. There was some trial and error that probably could have been avoided in the early days of the project if communication had been more proactive between the development team and Preservica.

There is an outstanding issue in that search results on the public-facing end of our Digital Collections are flooded with ledger data. The search function has been rendered ineffective as most searches will return a significant amount of ledger images as they contain so many potential keywords. For example, a search for 'bottle' returns 697 results and 324 of these relate to the ledgers, rather than our packaging collections. A search for 'Guinness' yields 30,634 results. We are working on a solution to filter out these results. One option is to retrospectively strip the descriptive metadata that was added to each image during the first attempt at mapping.

These obstacles are relatively minor in the overall scheme of the project and the search functionality powered by Preservica has been a huge win for the

Archive in terms of access in a digital preservation environment. The solution to provide a public facing search functionality powered by Preservica - which serves as a digital preservation system rather than a historical database - has allowed the Guinness Archive to publish this large dataset on-line with a user friendly interface to meet business needs, while maintaining the integrity of the digital preservation environment to meet the needs of the Guinness Archive.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Leanne Harrington is Digital Archivist at the Guinness Archive in Dublin, Ireland. Leanne has over a decade of experience with collections spanning medieval manuscripts to the world of Guinness. Leanne's focus turned to digital archives in January 2020 with a professional interest in access, outreach and preservation.

